

Escaping a Code Stroke: Evaluation of Escape Room Methodology on Acceptance of Stroke Management Guidelines

Diana Dauz Tai, DNP, RN, AGACNP-BC, ACNS-BC, CCRN, CNRN, SCRNP
Ayman Tailakh, PhD, RN and Cinthya Vasquez Sotelo, DNP, RN, FNP-C, ENP-C

Background

- Stroke is leading cause of morbidity
- 800,000 people who will experience a stroke annually in the U.S.
- More emphasis on timely recognition and reduction of delays to thrombolysis and endovascular treatment (thrombectomy)
- Delays to stroke interventions remain despite quality initiatives

Problem Statement

Workflow changes can lead to resistance of evidence-based guideline adoption; therefore, attitudes towards practice change should further be explored

Project Objectives

- Increase new hire nurses' knowledge base regarding current American Heart/American Stroke (AHA/ASA) 2019 Acute Ischemic Stroke Management Guidelines
- Increase overall attitudes towards adherence to stroke guidelines
- Pilot a new method of education

Stroke Escape Room

- 5 puzzles and clues based on the AHA/ASA 2019 Acute Ischemic Stroke Guidelines
- Each clue represented a critical component of the stroke management workflow for expedited treatment.

Theoretical Framework: Theory of Planned Behavior

Methods

- Step 1 Discovery Research:** Performed extensive literature review on stroke escape room methodology
- Step 2 Evidence Summary:** Implementation of an escape room led to improved learner attitudes and confidence
- Step 3 Translation to Guidelines:** Designing of Escape Room
- Step 4 Practice Integration:** Implementation of Escape Room during nursing orientation
- Step 5 Process, Outcome, Evaluation:** Data collection and analysis using the Evidence-Based Practice Attitude Scale (EBPAS)

Data Analysis/Results

*Cronbach's Alpha: 0.854 / Paired t-test: p= 0.014

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics: Total Participants (40)

Measure	Percentage (N)
Gender	
Female	80% (32)
Age	
22-30	53% (21)
31-40	38% (5)
50+	10% (4)
Employment Status	
Full-Time	100% (40)
Level of Education	
Bachelor's Degree	97.5% (39)
Associate degree	2.50% (1)
Job Title	
Staff Nurse	93% (37)
Specialty	
Emergency Medicine	41% (16)
Stroke Experience	68% (27)
Experience with 2019 AHA/ASA Stroke Guidelines	52.5% (21)
Certification Status	
Stroke Certified Registered Nurse	38% (5)
Years of Experience	
<2 years	57.5% (23)

Discussion/Conclusions

- Results of the paired-t test indicate a significant medium difference pre/post stroke escape room implementation
- Increased overall attitudes towards adoption of current stroke guidelines
- Implementation of escape room provides insight into the potential effectiveness of a non-traditional educational approach

Future Implications

- Integration of escape rooms in other avenues of nursing education: nursing orientation, unit-based onboarding processes, skills days
- Correlation between experience vs non-experienced (New Graduate) nurses/generational differences

References

Scan Code

